

The river floodplain area of Uttar Pradesh State occupies nearly 1.5 million ha; main rivers are the Ganga, Yamuna, Sarda, Gomti, Saryu, and Gandak. The Gomti accounts for 0.20 million ha. Adopting cropping sequences of rice - mustard or rice - wheat could significantly improve its agriculture. □

Rice cultivation practices in a Negrito foraging society in northeastern Luzon, Philippines

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The Casiguran Agta, a Negrito population in northeastern Luzon, Philippines, are nomadic hunters and gatherers. Many households, however, also make swiddens (slash-and-burn fields), and a few cultivate wet rice paddies. In 1984, 609 Agta were living in a 700-m² rainforest area in northern Aurora Province. Rainfall averages 3,448 mm/yr.

For 19 mo in 1983-84, we studied Agta cultivation practices by measuring and recording crop data and interviewing field owners. It was a good year, with no significant crop damage from insects or weather. Twenty-two percent of households planted crops, sharing harvests with others. They cultivated 43 swiddens and 5 irrigated rice paddies.

The Agta spend little time in agriculture. Overall, men and women gave 6% of their days to this task (range 0-36%). Total cropped area was 8.6 ha, 91% in rice, only 141 m² per capita. Rice cropping was 128 m² per capita. Mean swidden size was 0.14 ha (s.d.: 0.11 ha), mean paddy size was 0.53 ha.

Total annual rough rice production was 9.1 t, 4.7 t from swiddens and 4.4 t from paddies, enough to feed the population for only 15 d. Mean rough rice yield from swiddens was 0.9 t/ha (n=17). One paddy yielded 1.7 t/ha.

The Agta planted 10 different rice varieties in the swiddens. They grew 47 cultivars of all crops in swiddens, averaging 7.5 cultivars/ swidden, including rice (s.d.: 6.3, range: 1-27).

To our knowledge, the Agta have the smallest swiddens of any cultural group in SE Asia (1/7 ha), the fewest rice varieties/ swidden (1.5), and the fewest cultivars/swidden (7.5). Though they eat rice at 92% of their meals, only 5% of

the rice they eat comes from their own fields. They secure most of it by trading minor forest products and through casual wage labor for outsiders. The Agta cultivate rice mainly as a hobby and for prestige, rather than to produce food. They are not farmers, and since Spanish records show they were making swiddens in the 1700s, they are not evolving from foraging to farming. □

Cassava varieties for 5-mo summer rice fallow in Kerala

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Extensive rice areas in Kerala have a pattern of two rice crops—one medium-duration rice for rainy (May-Aug) season and one long-duration for dry season (Aug-Dec)—followed by a 5-mo summer fallow. We tested five cassava

varieties for summer fallow in a replicated yield trial during summer 1987. We used 75- × 75-cm spacing, 50-50-50 kg NPK/ ha, a basal application of cattle manure at 12.5 t/ ha, and irrigation every 2 wk.

Varieties Co 2 (recently released from Tamil Nadu) and M4 (already popular in Kerala for a 9-10 mo season) are suited to the 5-mo summer rice fallow season under Kerala conditions (see table). □

Performance of 5 cassava varieties in the 5-mo summer rice fallow season. Pattambi, Kerala, 1987.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Tuber yield (t/ha)	Tuber characteristics		
			Length (cm)	Girth (cm)	Softening on cooking
Co 2	102	12.6	22	12	Very good
M4	123	11.6	22	11	Very good
Malavella	117	10.0	26	12	Very good
12/77	141	9.1	25	11	Good
11/76	124	10.3	24	12	Good
LSD (P = 0.05)	—	2.0	—	—	—

Data management and computer modeling

Modeling feeding rates of rice leaffolder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* on different plant stages

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The rice LF damages plants by feeding on the leaves, removing patches of photosynthetic tissue. Daily leaf area

consumed can be measured by exposing larvae of known age to susceptible rice. The cumulative consumption by a larva at age *t* represents the total leaf consumption from hatching to that age.

The first three instars fed little. More than 90% of feeding was done by the 4th and 5th instars age 11-19 d after hatching. The data fit an exponential model extremely well. The model is

$$C_t = e^{\beta t} - 1.0$$

Parameters of data fitted to the model $C_t = e^{\beta t} - 1.0$ relating the total leaf area consumed (cm^2) larva with larval age in days at different plant stages.^a IRRI, 1988.

Plant stage (DAS) ^b	$\beta \pm \text{SE}$	Goodness of fit ^c	
		MSR	VR
40	0.1815 \pm 0.0007	6205**	3820**
60	0.1692 \pm 0.0007	7673**	7438**
80	0.1536 \pm 0.0009	3487**	10929**
100	0.1360 \pm 0.0011	2024**	8547**

^a β = feeding rate coefficient and SE at 95% confidence. ^bDAS = days after sowing. ^cMSR = mean square ratio of mean squares for regression and residual from nonlinear curve fitting, VR = variance ratio from regression analysis of linearized data. ** = significance at P = 0.001.

Relationship between leaf consumption, age of LF larvae, and plant stages. IRRI, 1988.

where C_t is the age-specific total leaf area consumed from age 0 to age t and β is the feeding rate.

Feeding rates differed significantly for plants of different ages (see table). The rate constants related well to the plant stages expressed in days after sowing (DAS) by a linear model = 0.213 - 0.0008*DAS ($r^2 = 0.99$). Combining the two models, the relationships between leaf area consumption, age of LF larva, and plant stage can be shown (see figure). On plants 40 DAS, the LF larva could consume as much as 30 cm^2 leaf area, while on plants 100 DAS, it could consume only 11.5 cm^2 .

Since the leaf area consumed by LF larvae can be quantified using these two models, the effects of the pest's damage may now be computer simulated using an existing rice growth model. This coupling will allow us to predict yield reductions by a known population. □

The International Rice Research Newsletter is mailed free to individuals and institutions engaged in rice research and training. For further information, write IRRI, Communication and Publications Dept., Division R, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

ANNOUNCEMENTS

Irrigation symposium planned

An Asian Regional Symposium on *Modernisation and rehabilitation of irrigation and drainage schemes* is scheduled 13-15 Feb 1989 at the Development Academy of the Philippines.

The symposium is planned to encourage a dialogue among the various disciplines involved at all stages of irrigation and drainage rehabilitation. Papers presented on scheme selection, design, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation will include case studies. Specialists in engineering, agriculture,

economics, and the social sciences will participate.

Papers selected for the symposium are based largely on the Asian experience. Invited papers from other parts of the world will show different approaches to solving common problems in different environments.

Organizers and sponsors are Hydraulics Research Limited, Wallingford, England; National Irrigation Administration, Manila, Philippines; Overseas Development Administration, London; and Asian Development Bank, Manila.

Copies of papers, special lectures, and

discussion reports will be available from the Overseas Development Unit, Hydraulics Research, Wallingford, Oxfordshire OX10 8BA England. Copies are free to organizations in developing countries; individuals pay £25. □

Origin of Cultivated Rice

This book by Hiko-Ichi Oka, National Institute of Genetics, Mishima City, Japan, updates current understanding of the origin of cultivated rice, from biological and archaeological-historical perspectives. Recent discoveries are reviewed and new questions posed.

The content emphasizes ecological and genetical aspects, comparing the